

Implementation of the Policy on The Appointment and Dismissal of Village Apparatus at The Service of Community and Village Empowerment Pasangkayu District

(Study of the Appointment and Dismissal of Bulubonggu Village Officials, Dapurang Sub-District)

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Abstract

This research examines the Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials at the Community and Village Empowerment Service of Pasangkayu Regency by studying the Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Bulubonggu, Dapurang sub-District using George C. Edward III's policy implementation model which departs from the phenomenon of post-election appointment and dismissal of Village Apparatus. Village Heads simultaneously. The research method uses a qualitative descriptive approach and determines informants using purposive sampling. The research informants were the Head of Service and staff at the Postingkayu Regency Community and Village Empowerment Service Office, the Secretary of the Dapurang District Head, the Head of Bulubonggu Village, and the Chair of the BPD of Bulubonggu Village. Data collection uses observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis uses Miles and Huberman's interactive model approach, namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion verification. The research results show that: (1) The Pasangkayu Regency Government has not carried out special outreach regarding policy material for the appointment and dismissal of village officials. (2) There is no budget specifically allocated to implement the policy on appointing and dismissing Village Officials. (3) There are no Standard Operating Procedures made in the form of Regent's Regulations which serve as a reference for implementers at the Village level. Based on the dimensions of policy implementation, the George C. Edward III model is an inseparable system, so if there are still things that are not fulfilled among these systems, it can be concluded that the implementation of the policy has not been effective.

Keywords: communication, resources, disposition, bureaucratic structure.

Introduction

Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages has given very broad authority to Villages in regulating and managing Village interests in accordance with their authority which includes authority based on rights of origin, local village-scale authority, authority assigned by the Government, Provincial Government, or Regency/City Regional Government as well as other

authorities assigned by the Government, Provincial Regional Government, or Regency/City Regional Government in accordance with regulatory provisions. Apart from that, in order to complement Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, the Government has also issued various implementing regulations in the form of Government Regulations (PP) and related Ministerial Regulations (Permen), so that the Law can be implemented in the field. Very broad authority accompanied by the provision of a fairly large budget to all villages in Indonesia as well as fairly complete implementing regulations governing Village Government governance starting from village planning, implementation of village development, village financial management, village administration system, drafting village legal products and so on. etc., requires the capacity of the Village Apparatus to be strong and adequate, to be able to carry out all of these authorities well and with quality in accordance with all the regulatory provisions that govern them.

One of the Village Head's authorities is to appoint and dismiss Village Officials, this is stated in Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages in article 26 paragraph (2) letter b, it is stated that the Village Head in carrying out his duties has the authority to appoint and dismiss Village Apparatus. Article 48 explains that the Village Apparatus consists of the Village Secretariat, regional implementers and technical implementers. Article 49 states that the Village Apparatus as referred to above – is tasked with assisting the Village Head in carrying out his duties and authority.

The appointment and dismissal of Village Officials is further regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 83 of 2015 concerning the Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials.

The existence of the Village Apparatus profession before 2019 was less attractive to the general public because most people thought that this position was occupied by people closest to the Village Head, but since the issuance of Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11 of 2019 concerning the Second Amendment to Government Regulation Number 43 2014 concerning Implementing Regulations of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages which regulates improving the welfare of Village Heads and Village Apparatus. Government Regulation Number 11 of 2019 states that the fixed income of Village Heads and Village Apparatus is budgeted in the Village APBD which is sourced from the Village Fund Allocation (ADD), the amount of which is almost equivalent to the salary of Class II State Civil Servants (ASN). This is one of the triggers so that the Village Apparatus profession is starting to become popular with village communities.

Of course, with the great interest of the community who want to become Village Officials, the Village Government must be selective in the recruitment process, there are general qualifications and special requirements that must be fulfilled by prospective applicants and even a competency test needs to be added to get qualified Village Applicant candidates to work in Village Government.

Pasangkayu Regency (formerly North Mamuju Regency) is one of them Level II Region in Province West Sulawesi. Capital Regency This is located in the District Install wood. Pasangkayu Regency was previously part of Mamuju Regency which then through Law Number

7 of 2003, Pasangkayu Regency was expanded into an autonomous Regency called North Mamuju Regency. However, based on Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 61 of 2019, North Mamuju Regency changed its name to Pasangkayu Regency. Since its founding, Pasangkayu Regency has experienced quite significant developments in the field of government, where initially it consisted of 4 (four) sub-districts but in 2007, through the Pasangkayu Regency Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2007, it was expanded into 12 (twelve) sub-districts consisting of from 59 (fifty nine) villages and 4 (four) sub-districts.

Based on our initial observations in Pasangkayu Regency, West Sulawesi Province, since 2019 there have been 3 (three) simultaneous Village Head Elections held. First in 2019 there were 22 (twenty two) villages, second in 2022 there were 35 (thirty five) villages and finally in August 2023 there were 3 (three) villages that followed. The current phenomenon is that after the Village Head Election, most of the Village Governments that have carried out Village Head Elections have overhauled the structure of their Village Apparatus. Furthermore, the researcher received information that in Bulubonggu Village, Dapurang District, Pasangkayu Regency, which was the location of our research, the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials had been carried out 2 (two) times in the last 3 years, namely in 2020 and at the beginning of 2023.

In accordance with Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, Article 26 paragraph (2) letter b explains that a Village Head has the authority to appoint and dismiss Village Officials. Article 48 explains that the Village Apparatus consists of the Village Secretariat, regional implementers and technical implementers. Article 49 states that the Village Apparatus as referred to above is tasked with assisting the Village Head in carrying out his duties and authority,

Based on the explanation above, the researcher is interested in conducting research entitled "Implementation of Policies for the Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials at the Community and Village Empowerment Service of Pasangkayu Regency (Study of the Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Bulubonggu, Dapurang District)". This polemic became the basis for the researcher to raise this issue as material and the title of the thesis as a requirement for completing Master's Postgraduate Studies.

Based on the Problem Formulation as described above, the aim of this research is to analyze the Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in the Community and Village Empowerment Service of Pasangkayu Regency (Study of Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Bulubonggu, Dapurang District).

Previous Research

Before conducting research, researchers make observations to find writings or literature that are relevant to the research to be carried out. The research related to the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials that has been carried out by previous researchers is research by Nuraisyah (2020) with the title Desertation of Implementation of the Building Permit Policy in Palu City. This research is about the implementation of building permit policies in Palu City. In this research, the author uses the theory of George C. Edward III (1980) and the method used in this research is a qualitative descriptive research method. This research took data from 11 (eleven) informants who were selected using purposive sampling, taking the research location in

Palu City. With the conclusion that (1) the communication aspect to socialize the processing of building permits has not been implemented optimally; (2) the resource aspect is adequate in terms of quality, but in terms of quantity and budget resources and facilities it is inadequate; (3) the disposition aspect is shown by the attitude of implementers who support the policy, but there is still overlapping work on the part of spatial planning and land management; and (4) aspects of the bureaucratic structure already have clarity in the form of standard operational procedures, but have not been implemented effectively because there is no control or control over the implementation of policies and there are no strict sanctions for development carried out by the people of Palu City, especially people who do not yet have building permits. building..

Public Policy Concept

In essence, there are many meanings or definitions of public policy that can be found in various literature on public policy. Each of these definitions has different emphasis. This difference arises because of differences in background or point of view in understanding public policy.

The term policy in English is differentiated from the word wisdom which means wisdom or discernment. Policy is a general statement of behavior of an organization. In the opinion of Alfonsus Sirait in his book Management defines policy as follows: "Policy is a guideline for decision making" (Sirait, 1991:115). Policy is something that is useful and is also a simplification of the system that can help and reduce problems and a series of actions to solve certain problems, therefore a policy is considered very important.

William N. Dunn mentions the term public policy in his book entitled Public Policy Analysis, the meaning is as follows: "Public Policy is a complex pattern of interdependent collective choices, including decisions not to act, which made by a government agency or office" (Dunn, 2003: 132).

Public policy according to what Dunn put forward implies the existence of collective choices that depend on each other, which includes decisions to take action. The public policy in question is made by a government agency or office. Once a policy has been created, it must be implemented to be implemented by administrative units that mobilize financial and human resources, and evaluated so that it can be used as a monitoring mechanism for the policy in accordance with the objectives of the policy itself.

Edward III and Sharkansky stated that public policy is: "What government says and does, or not to do, it is the goals or purpose of government programs. (what is said and done, or not done. Policy is a series of goals and objectives of the program -government programs)" (Following Widodo, 2001:190).

Edward III and Sharkansky's opinions indicate what was done or not done. This is related to the goals and targets contained in the programs created by the government. Miriam Budiardjo stated that the definition of policy is a collection of decisions taken by an actor or by a political group in an effort to choose goals and methods to achieve those goals (Budiardjo, 2008: 56). Based on the definition above, policy is a collection of decisions. This decision is taken by an

actor or by a political group, namely the government. This decision seeks to choose goals and ways to achieve the goals you want to achieve.

Public Policy Implementation

Policy implementation is a further process from the policy formulation stage. At the formulation stage, policy strategies and objectives are determined, while actions to achieve the objectives are carried out at the policy implementation stage. In developed countries, a policy is generally debated during its formulation in parliament because the public is included so that once the policy has been issued there is no longer any debate in society. Meanwhile, in developing countries it is debated in society during implementation because the people are not included in policy formulation. In this regard, Tachjan (2006.:vi) emphasized that: "Public policy implementation is a complex process, involving organizational, leadership and even managerial dimensions from the government as the authority holder".

The complexity of the problem of policy implementation was also stated by Agustino (2006: 153) that: "In practice, policy implementation is a process that is so complex that it often even has a political content due to intervention from various interests". To illustrate the complexity of the policy implementation process, he cited opinions from Eugene Bardach in Agustino (2006:613) states: "It is enough to create a program and general policy that looks good on paper. It is even more difficult to formulate it with words and slogans that sound pleasing to the ears of leaders and voters listen to it. And it is even more difficult to carry it out in a form that satisfies everyone."

Several Policy Implementation Models

To clarify understanding of the implementation of public policy, there are two approaches, namely the top down and bottom up approaches. In the opinion of Lester and Stewart (2000), this term is called the command and control approach. Each approach proposes a framework model in establishing the link between policy and its results.

Several experts and experts adhere to the top down approach, such as Marilee S. Grindle, George C. Edward III, Daniel A. Mazmanian and Paul A. Sabatier, Van Meter and Van Horn. They all stated that the success of policy implementation will be determined by many variables or factors, and each of these variables is related to each other. To enrich our understanding of the various variables involved in implementation, several theories will be collaborated below:

George C. Edward III Policy Implementation Model

According to George C. Edwards III (in Subarsono, 2006;90-92 and Winarno, 2008;175-221) there are factors that influence policy implementation, namely:

- a. **Communication:** The first condition for the implementation of a policy to be effective is that the policy must be conveyed or known to the people who are entrusted with the duties and responsibilities to implement it clearly. Of course, in this case accurate communication is needed and implemented appropriately by policy implementers. Implementing public policy in order to achieve success requires that the implementer knows what must be done clearly.

What are the goals and objectives of the policy must be informed to the target group so that implementation distortion will be reduced.

- b. **Resource:** In implementing policies, resources must be supported, including human resources, materials and methods. Even though the targets, objectives and contents of the policy have been communicated clearly and consistently, if the implementer lacks the resources to implement it, implementation will not be effective and efficient. Resources are an important factor for effective and efficient policy implementation. Edward III categorized organizational resources as consisting of staff, information, authority, facilities, buildings, equipment, land and supplies. Each element included in the organizational resource variable is related to each other in optimizing the role of resources in the implementation process. If one of the resource elements does not work well, it will result in weak performance of the existing resource elements.
- c. **Disposition:** A disposition in implementation and characteristics, attitudes possessed by policy implementers, such as commitment, honesty, clever communicativeness and democratic nature. A good implementer must have a good disposition, then he will carry out the policy well as desired and determined by the policy maker. Likewise, if the behavior or perspectives of implementers differ from those of policy or decision makers, then the process of implementing a policy becomes increasingly difficult.
- d. **Bureaucratic Structure:** The existence of a bureaucratic structure is very necessary to support the performance of resources and stakeholders related to the policy implementation process by means of a clear division of tasks and responsibilities so that there is no imbalance in tasks in the process.

These four factors can influence directly or indirectly an implementation. Furthermore, policy implementation is the policy-making stage between the formation of the policy and the consequences for the community it influences. If a policy is inappropriate or cannot influence problems that arise even though it has been implemented, it will fail.

Method

This research uses a qualitative descriptive method to describe phenomena related to policies regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials. The research was conducted in three locations: the Pasangkayu Regency Village Community Empowerment Service Office, the Dapurang District Office, and Bulubonggu Village in Dapurang District, for three months from the issuance of the research permit until the completion of data collection and analysis. The type of data used consists of primary data involving responses from the Village Head, community leaders, and leaders at the District Office and Village Community Empowerment Service, as well as secondary data from the village, district, and relevant literature. Data was collected through observation, interviews and documentation. Determining informants used purposive sampling and snowball sampling techniques, with key informants including leaders at the Pasangkayu Regency Village Community Empowerment Service Office, leaders at the Dapurang District Office, the Head of Bulubonggu Village, and community leaders in

Bulubonggu Village. Data analysis follows the theory of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2014) which involves three steps: data condensation, data presentation, and conclusion drawing/verification. In this process, data is collected through observation, interviews, and documentation, then condensed through selection, narrowing, summarization, and simplification to focus on relevant data. The condensed data is presented in a structured manner to make it easier to draw conclusions, and these conclusions are verified with field evidence. This method allows researchers to comprehensively describe and analyze the appointment and dismissal policies of village officials.

Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency

According to George Edward III, the important stages of a public policy are in the policy implementation process itself. So far, policy implementation has been considered only as a stage of implementation of what has been decided by the Government or decision/policy makers, as if this stage does not have a major influence on the outcome of a decision. In fact, if we interpret it more deeply, in reality this implementation stage is very important because a policy will not mean anything if the implementation stage is not carried out properly and correctly according to established procedures. In the sense that implementation is the stage where the policy product must be implemented optimally and as well as possible in order to achieve the targets that have been previously set.

The Central Government through the Ministry of Home Affairs has issued a policy in the form of a Minister of Home Affairs Regulation which regulates the Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials which applies generally throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. This policy has been issued twice, firstly through Minister of Home Affairs Regulation number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials, and secondly through Minister of Home Affairs Regulation number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials, which is currently still in effect. enforced and becomes a reference for the Regency Government, Subdistrict Government and Village Government in carrying out the process of appointing and dismissing Village Apparatus. Apart from that, the Regency Government, especially Pasangkayu Regency (at that time still North Mamuju Regency) has also issued a policy in the form of North Mamuju Regency Regional Regulation number 4 of 2017 which is a derivative of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia.

These policies are used as guidelines for the Pasangkayu Regency Government in regulating the provisions regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials within the scope of the Pasangkayu Regency administrative area. The Community and Village Empowerment Service or what is usually called the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service is the leading sector of the Village Government, so specifically the implementation of policies

regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials at the Regency level comes down to the PMD Service.

At the start of the research, the author explored information related to policies that serve as guidelines for the implementation of the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency. Based on the results of an interview with one of the staff (Muhammad Sarjan, S.Sos) at the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service Office, who previously served as Head of the Village Government Administration Division at the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service from 2013 to the end of 2022. In the interview he explained related The policies used as guidelines by the Pasangkayu Regency Government are as follows:

"The regulations that guide the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency are:

1. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials;
2. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials;
3. North Mamuju Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2017 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials."

(interview: Monday, January 15 2024)

Likewise with our interview with Mr. Dr. Drs. Irfan Rusli Sadek, M.Si as Head of the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service in a separate room, here are the results of his interview: "The regulations that we guide regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency are:

- a. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials;
- b. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials;
- c. North Mamuju Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2017 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials."

(interview: Monday, January 15 2024)

A similar statement was also expressed by the Head of Bulubonggu Village, Dapurang District (Arwin Rusdi, S.Sy., NL.P), from the results of his interview, he stated that: "The regulations that we, the Village Government, guide in terms of appointing and dismissing Village Officials are:

- a. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials;
- b. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials; as well as

- c. North Mamuju Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2017 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials."

(interview: Monday, January 22 2024)

The three informants above were supported by almost identical answers from the Secretary of the Subdistrict Head at the Dapurang District Office (BUDI SARWONO, S.Sy), from the results of the interview he stated that: "The regulations that guide the appointment and dismissal of village officials by the Subdistrict Government in Pasangkayu Regency is :

- a. Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 67 of 2017 concerning Amendments to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 83 of 2015 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials; as well as
- b. North Mamuju Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2017 concerning Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials."

(interview: Monday, January 22 2024)

The statement that most surprised the researchers came from the Chairman of the Bulubonggu Village Consultative Body (BPD) (Andi Tenri Sanna), who is a partner of the Bulubonggu Village Government, from the results of his interview, he stated that: "I don't understand the policy that is used as a reference for the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials. in Bulubonggu Village." (interview: Monday, January 22 2024).

From this initial interview, the researcher became increasingly curious about the implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency, especially in Bulubonggu Village, Dapurang District. The question now is, how can the process of implementing this policy be carried out as best as possible to achieve the main objectives as outlined in the policy that has been published? Therefore, in this research the author uses the George Edward III Implementation Model as an analytical tool used in looking at the implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials in the Community and Village Empowerment Service of Pasangkayu Regency, especially in Bulubonggu Village, Dapurang District, which is the locus of the author's research. George Edward III explained that there are 4 (four) variables that are supporting indicators in the successful implementation of a public policy, namely Communication, Resources, Disposition/Attitude of the Implementer and Bureaucratic Structure. For this reason, below the author provides a description of the results of research related to the Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials at the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service (Study of Appointment and Dismissal of Village Apparatus Bulubonggu, Dapuurang District) based on 4 (four) indicators according to George Edward III.

Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency in terms of Communication Aspects

Communication is very important in carrying out policy implementation. In the communication process, if the information conveyed is not conveyed well, the implementation process may be hampered and various problems may arise in the future. In this case, the first

responsibility for the policy maker is to convey policy information to the Implementors or Policy Implementors who will later implement the policy.

According to George Edward III, factors that influence policy implementation work simultaneously and interact with each other to help and hinder policy implementation, so the ideal approach is to reflect this complexity by discussing all of these factors at once. Communications relating to policy decisions and orders must be routed to the appropriate personnel before they can be followed. Of course, communication must be accurate and must be carefully understood by implementers. However, there are many.

According to George Edward III, consistency in government communication is very important in implementing policies because if it is not consistent in communicating policies regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials to the Village Government and District Government, it can cause confusion and uncertainty among implementers at the village and sub-district levels.

From the presentation of the interview results of the informants above, it shows that the implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency, seen from the communication aspect, according to George Edward III, is still not implemented optimally. This is because there are still obstacles being experienced, including the absence of socialization that specifically discusses policies relating to the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials as well as Regional Regulation policies that have not been updated following the latest Minister of Home Affairs Regulations, giving rise to unclear orders reaching implementers at the level. village.

Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency in terms of the Resource Aspect

Resources in implementing policies are like a machine, which will not function properly if there is less/minimal oil. According to Nugroho (2012:22), resources consist of Human Resources, Financial Resources, Authority Resources and Infrastructure. Meanwhile, Van Meter and Van Horn (1983:22) divide resources into human resources, material resources and method resources. The implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency has not been fully supported by all these resources. This is proven by the results of interviews with several informants in the field.

In implementing the policy of appointing and dismissing Village Officials, resources are needed to support implementation, especially those related to human resources and financial resources. According to George Edward III's implementation model, every policy must be supported by adequate human and financial resources. Human resources are the adequacy of both quantity and quality of policy implementers. Financial resources are the availability and adequacy of funds for implementing a policy. The results of the research show that human resources for implementing the policy of appointing and dismissing Village Officials at the Pasangkayu Regency Community and Village Empowerment Service are sufficient in quantity and quality. However, financial resources are still inadequate because the budget allocation

provided in relation to the implementation of the policy on appointing and dismissing Village Officials has not been allocated. Even though it is supported by adequate human resources, if it is not supported by sufficient financial resources, the implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials will not be carried out effectively.

Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency in terms of the Disposition Aspect

The disposition in policy implementation by George Edwards III is intended as a unified understanding between policy implementation and direction from leader (superior). These limitations can also be caused by the indifference of policy implementers. Disposition according to George Edwards III (1980:32) can be divided into several indicators, namely the direct implementer as referred to in this research, the Village Head as the executor in the process of implementing the appointment and dismissal of Village Apparatus, the District Government as the verifier and issuing Recommendation Letters and the Community Empowerment Service and Villages in the Regency as a control function for implementing policies in the field. This is intended to avoid misleading regarding the authority carried out.

From various statements regarding the implementation of the policy on appointing and dismissing village officials in Pasangkayu Regency, if viewed from the disposition aspect, it has actually been running in accordance with existing policy regulations, both in terms of the division of authority and so on. My only problem in this case goes back to resources, both human resources and financial resources, and communication to the lower level needs to be carried out so that implementers at the village level and target groups can understand the contents of the policy.

Implementation of the Policy for Appointment and Dismissal of Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency in terms of the Bureaucratic Structure Aspect

Bureaucracy is important in implementing the policy of appointing and dismissing Village Officials in Pasangkayu Regency. There are two main characteristics in a bureaucratic structure, namely: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and Fragmentation. Bureaucratic structure can influence the successful implementation of a policy. Policy implementation is a quite complex process that requires strong and conducive bureaucratic cooperation. If resources are sufficient, then to implement a policy and implementers know what must be done and want to do it, implementation can still be thwarted due to deficiencies in the bureaucratic structure. Organizational fragmentation can hinder the coordination necessary to successfully implement complex policies that require the cooperation of many people, and may also waste scarce resources, hinder change, create confusion, cause policies to work at cross-purposes, and result in critical functions being compromised. neglected (Edwards II (in Kadji, 2015: 66).

The mechanism for implementing the Minister of Home Affairs Regulations and Regional Regulations related to the implementation of policies on the appointment and dismissal of Village

Officials in Pasangkayu Regency, has so far been running in accordance with Standard Operating Procedures (SOP), where the technical instructions for implementation are outlined in the form of a Regent's Circular Letter as a follow-up to the Minister of Home Affairs Regulations and Regulations. The area in question.

From the results of our interview with the Secretary of the Dapurang District Head, it shows that the Regent's Circular which according to the Pasangkayu Regency PMD Service can be used as a reference to replace SOPs is in fact not yet effective because 2 (two) villages out of the 5 (five) villages in Dapurang District still misinterpret it, even almost do not understand the procedures for appointing and dismissing Village Officials. One of the reasons for this is the lack of socialization regarding existing policies and the rules that follow these policies.

The existence of this SOP is actually very important, as stated by Brother Muhammad Sarjan, S.Sos, that SOPs must be made based on Regent Regulations or so on, which usually state who carries out what, so that the direction of the implementers' tasks can be clearer and more focused. Relevant Regional Apparatus Organizations can also determine when and where they should be in implementing policies regarding the appointment and dismissal of Village Apparatus.

Conclusion

Judging from the dimensions of policy implementation of the George Edward III model (communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure) it shows that the implementation of the policy for appointing and dismissing Village Officials in the Community and Village Empowerment Service of Pasangkayu Regency with a study of appointing and dismissing Village Apparatus in Bulubonggu, Dapurang District in Basically it has been implemented but is still not effective. This is because there are still shortcomings in several aspects. Among other things, from the communication aspect, there have been no socialization activities that specifically discuss and deepen material related to policies governing the appointment and dismissal of Village Officials, and also regarding clarity of policy content, there is still a lack of synchronization between the Minister of Home Affairs Regulations and Regional Regulations which are derivatives of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation itself, so that Flaws emerged that were misused by implementers at the village level. From a resource aspect, it is not yet fully supported by financial/budget resources. And from the aspect of bureaucratic structure, there are no Standard Operating Procedures made in the form of Regent's Regulations so that there are still implementers at the village level who do not understand the procedures for appointing and dismissing Village Officials. As is known, the policy implementation dimension of George Edward III's model is an inseparable system, so if there are still things that are not fulfilled, it can be concluded that the implementation of the policy has not been effective.

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